

Metallic Compounds of the Schiff Base derived from 5-Formyl-oxine and Benzidine

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The present communication describes the synthesis of the compounds of the bis-schiff base from 5-formyl-oxine and benzidine with metallic ions like Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} . Probable structures of the compounds have been discussed from thermal stability and infrared spectral data.

IN a previous communication¹, we have reported the compounds of the Schiff base derived from 5-formyl-oxine and para-phenylene diamine. The present communication deals with the compounds of the closely allied Schiff base derived from 5-formyl-oxine and benzidine.

Experimental

5-Formyl-oxine was prepared by the method described by Clemo and Howe². The product on recrystallisation from ethanol yielded straw coloured needles melting at 172°-173°. Preparation of the compounds of the Schiff base with metals :

Cu(II) , Ni(II) , Co(II) , Mn(II) , Zn(II) , Cd(II) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$. Compounds were prepared following the general method outlined below :

The mixture of 5-formyl-oxine (0.01 mole), metal-acetate hydrate (0.005 mole) and benzidine (0.005 mole) was dissolved in hot dimethyl formamide. A coloured solution often accompanied by the separation of a small amount of a coloured solid resulted.

The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 2 hr and then concentrated to a small volume on water-bath and cooled to room temperature. Cold water was then added to the concentrated refluxate when highly coloured solid compound separated out. This was kept in a refrigerator for several hours and the precipitated compound was collected on a filter, washed with water and alcohol and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride. The substances were in most cases amorphous in nature.

Analysis :

The nitrogen contents of the compounds were determined by Dumas method and the metal contents by conventional methods of volumetry and gravimetry. Results of analyses are given in Table 1.

Solubility of the Compounds :

All the compounds were insoluble in water and organic solvents like alcohol, acetone, benzene,

TABLE I. ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF THE COMPOUNDS

Composition	Calcd. %		Found %	
	N	Metal	N	Metal
[CU L.2 H ₂ O] (Deep brown)	9.46	10.74	9.22	10.81
[NiL.2H ₂ O] (Yellowish brown)	9.54	10.00	9.57	9.82
[CoL.2 H ₂ O] (Reddish brown)	9.54	10.06	9.62	9.72
[MnL.2 H ₂ O] (Reddish brown)	9.60	9.43	9.25	9.30
[ZnL.2 H ₂ O] (Yellowish orange)	9.43	11.03	9.10	10.52
[CdL] (Orange-yellow)	9.26	18.60	9.06	18.82
[UO ₂ L] (Deep red)	7.35	31.23	7.05	30.70

L = C₃₂H₂₀O₂N₄ i.e. one molecule of the Schiff base minus two portions.

chloroform, etc. They were appreciably soluble in hot D.M.F. All the compounds were quite stable in hot dilute alkali, but were partly soluble in dil. mineral acids on gentle heating on waterbath. They were, however, completely soluble in boiling mineral acids.

Thermal decomposition studies on the compounds :

The effect of heat on these compounds upto the decomposition point were studied by the method already described in details in a previous communication³. The weight-loss percentages were plotted against temperatures in each case and the respective thermal decomposition curve was thus obtained (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Thermal decomposition curves of 5-formyl-8-hydroxy quinoline-benzidine-metal complexes.
A—A = Cu²⁺, B = Ni²⁺, C = Co²⁺, D = Mn²⁺
B—E = Zn²⁺, F = Cd²⁺, G = UO₂²⁺.

Discussion

The condensation product of 5-formyl-oxine and benzidine can be isolated in the form of bis-Schiff base as a yellow powder (containing two moles of 5-formyl-oxine and one mole of benzidine) but due to its sparing solubility even in hot dimethyl formamide, the metal chelates of this Schiff base were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde, benzidine and the metal acetate in D.M.F. The metallic compounds which have been obtained as highly coloured amorphous powders on addition of

water to the concentrated refluxates, correspond to the empirical composition ML₂H₂O where M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Zn(II) and ML, where M = Cd(II), UO₂²⁺ and LH₂ = a molecule of the bis-schiff base containing two moles of 5-formyl-oxine and one mole of benzidine. These products may be polymeric and associated with low molecular weight moieties like monomers of the composition M(LH)(OH)(H₂O) or dimers etc., but no convincing evidence regarding their polymeric nature has been obtained. That these compounds are of the bis-schiff base of 5-formyl-oxine and benzidine was shown by their infrared spectral data taken in Nujol mull and the observations are quite consistent with our previous results¹. The presence of the schiff base in these compounds is shown by a band at ~1520 cm⁻¹, which has been assigned to the absorption originating from C = N stretching vibration associated with the conjugated ring system⁴. The band at ~1080 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the vibrations of the

M—O—C << bond⁵ and the sharp band at ~1570

cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the <C = N- vibration of the quinoline ring after chelation. The presence of water in the compound is also indicated by a medium sharp band at 3540–3520 cm⁻¹ in the I.R. spectra.

Thermal decomposition studies of the metal-chelates show that they start decomposing at 325°–375°. Below this temperature, the weight-loss percentages are different for different compounds, ranging from 7.5 to 15.8%. These complexes are, therefore, not only comparatively much more stable thermally than the simpler chelates of Schiff bases, but also more stable than our previously reported compounds¹. It has been found from the weight-loss percentage data at different temperatures, that the Zn(II) compound is thermally the most stable as observed previously¹.

An examination of the thermal stability curves reveals that the initial slopes in the curve may be either due to the volatilisation of water and low molecular weight moieties present in the compounds or due to a slower rate of decomposition at lower temperatures. A rather sharp break in each curve probably points to the critical decomposition temperature (of the compounds) above which a fast rate of decomposition is noticed.

The actual molecular weights of the chelates and their degree of polymerisation could not be ascertained by usual cryoscopic methods for lack of their solubility in common solvents.

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